

PROJECT PARTNERS

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Horizon Europe Programme for Research and Innovation under the Grant Agreement N° 101057988

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SUSAAN

SUSustainable Antimicrobial
and Antiviral Nanocoating

New Sustainable Antiviral and Antimicrobial Nanocoating for textile, plastic and metallic high traffic objects, developing Active Nano Materials (ANMs) to improve efficiency, decreasing contact time and toxicity.

PROJECT DETAILS

Start Date: 01 June 2022

Duration: 42 months

Estimated Project Cost: €5,754,846.25

SUSAAN project aims to develop antiviral and antimicrobial surfaces including development of fast active response and durable surfaces, considering ease of use, low toxicity and health issues and finally targeting a global sustainability concept, understood as environmental, economic and social sustainability for the required product and application.

PROJECT WORK PLAN

- WP1 Specific definition of requirements
- WP2 Development and production of active nanomaterials
- WP3 Development and production of nano-coatings
- WP4 Application and testing on final products
- WP5 Toxicity, regulatory and sustainability assessment
- WP6 Dissemination, communication, and exploitation
- WP7 Project management

PROJECT OBJECTIVES

- **Developing a range of improved Active Nano Materials (ANMs) safely- tailored to the applications.**
- **Increasing fast performance and durability of the AM/AV coatings on high-traffic non-porous surfaces.**
- **Increasing sustainability and stability of the AM/AV coatings on textiles.**
- **Validating the scalability of the products and the pathways for commercialization.**

PROJECT METHODOLOGY

PROJECT IMPACT

 Scientific : New sustainable-by-design antimicrobial and antiviral coating with enhanced functionalities (durability, efficiency, low toxicity).

 Environmental : Integrated life cycle sustainability assessment (ILCSA) including LCA, LCC and SLCA will provide a practical approach to integrate and harmonize a parallel assessment of individual sustainability aspects by introducing common definitions, settings and system models.

 Economic : In the short term it is estimated that SUSAAN coatings are implemented in 30 companies, and afterwards this figure could be multiplied by 10 in the long term. This will impact on 95% of SMEs and on a sector that employs approximately 1.2 million people and 3.6 million indirectly.

 Social : The transition to sustainable chemicals will also be mindful of socio-economic consequences including employment impacts on specific regions, in three main market sectors through end users and workers.

